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“LIKE AND SUBSCRIBE”

In a tiny room of an old condominium lives Alena, an IT undergrad. She was once the top of her class but was just recently kicked-out of the university after being involved in a hacking incident. She was framed as a mastermind in a crime that she did not even do. Although she wasn't locked up in jail due lack of evidence, since then, her life has been a total mess. She encountered not just one but numerous rejections from other universities she tried to apply. What made her situation even worse is the fact that no institution wanted to hire her, even for just being a service crew, after being flashed in the local television, and branded as a “suspect” in a crime that she has no idea who did. Losing her studies, not being able to get a job, and being put under constant scrutiny, Alena chose to wrap herself up inside her room. “At least, they couldn't kick me out here, could they?” she muttered as she stared out of the window. “Who in the world planned to frame me like this? Who is my enemy?”

For months, Alena has been investigating who framed her. She promised herself never to return home unless she gives herself justice. After the incident, she knew, she couldn't rely on anyone in this place.

Since she couldn't find a job anywhere, she decided, she'd make money anyway! Good thing, she is smart, she knows her way through the internet world, her skills in programming and website creating silently helped her through.

One day, she came across a YouTube video that somehow depicted her own life. The theme was somewhat eerie; the content creator wore a mask and tells a story about a girl who was kicked out of a university after hacking through the school's grading system in order for her to remain on top of her class. Alena felt something strange. Yes, for just a few months ago, her name was all over the news but she believes that her story is not intriguing enough to be made into a content. Whoever made this video probably knows her personally. Showing interest about her, not to mention making a video about her is somehow scary. Alena scanned through the creator's YouTube channel. She was shocked to see that this creator gains millions of views from every video! She started to get curious, so she watched video after video, only to find out that every video has only one theme, and that is to bring the “hacker” down. Alena felt a sudden chill down her spine, are those videos talking about her or are there other girls out there who experienced the same thing as her. If so, does this make her a victim?

Alena is internet-wise, herself, so she investigated this content creator. She gathered data after data she think she would need in order to track this creator down. She downloaded every video in the channel and watched it multiple times in order to find clues. She's desperate to give herself justice but to no avail, she couldn't find any discrepancy in each video. She then started to think that this creator may have just found her story amusing that's why they created a video about it. She was about to give up but one video caught her attention. In a somehow blurry angle, she could see a portion of her condominium room while the creator said, “She did not know I have tracked her down.” She abruptly paused the video and looked under her table, under her bed, and across every corner of her tiny room, but she did not

find any hidden camera, whatsoever. She looked at the video again, paused it, and focused thinking, “Where could this angle be?”

After much thinking, Alena stood up, and went to the door. She slowly opened it in a forty-five-degree angle, and voila! Across the door hang a small mailbox which belongs to her neighbor, Mrs. Padilla. Alena looked up inside the mailbox, it was empty. She felt the bottom of the mailbox with her right hand and there she found a teeny-weeny camera. Now she is sure, the videos were all about her. But who is this stalker and what is this stalker’s intention? Is this creator the one who framed her? She ought to know.

Alena worked day and night figuring out every bit of clue, connecting every part of the puzzle, until all of it pointed to one specific person, Ysabelle. Ysabelle was Alena’s classmate and close rival. While Alena remained on top, Ysabelle remained on the second place. Is their school rivalry enough for Ysabelle to frame her? Is Ysabelle the one who framed her? She needed to find out so, Alena secretly sneaked into her old school during the evening. Scanning through school records and files, she found out that Ysabelle gained the top spot as soon as she was gone. That would be obvious because Ysabelle is smart but she needs to find out if Ysabelle was the one who framed her. Alena looked through the school directory and found Ysabelle’s address and phone number. She dialed. A girl answered after several ringing. “Hello?” sounded Ysabelle’s voice. Alena hurriedly hanged up, quickly went out of the school premises, and went to Ysabelle’s address. She was shocked when she found out that Ysabelle lives in a rooftop exactly facing her condominium room. Now she is certain, Ysabelle did frame her.

Upon laying down every evidence on the table, Alena planned her next move. She carefully created her own YouTube Channel. For days, she acted as one of Ysabelle’s avid subscribers, leaving a like, and a comment to every video she uploads every day. Until a new video is uploaded. The video showed how Ysabelle claimed to be the GOAT in the IT world because, she said, despite being a student, her fame and money right now is about to surpass that of Bill Gate’s. Now it is clear. This girl is hungry for fame and money. A total psychopath who is willing to destroy whoever she likes in order to get famous. But Alena is smarter. She was the original top student, right? She anonymously called a trusted detective while simultaneously playing the evidence video of Ysabelle’s crimes on a YouTube Live. Viewers immediately rose up to a million in fifteen minutes. This then led to the detective’s search for Ysabelle. She was arrested in her own house after being tracked down by the police. She had no choice but to surrender and admit all the crimes she had done but she showed no sign of remorse for doing all of it. She said, “I simply did it because that Alena girl kept on getting on to my nerves! I just figured I need her to taste a little misery, and to be honest, it was fun!”

Ysabelle was locked down in jail after facing various kinds of crimes for violating media laws and ethics, not to mention cybercrime which is a serious crime itself.

The detective thanked Alena for helping him catch the real culprit. Then Alena returned home, contented and satisfied upon giving herself the justice she deserves.

